

The Influence of Occupational Health and Safety on Employee Performance at The Westin Jakarta Hotel

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ABSTRACT

Occupational health and safety is an important factor that influences employee performance, especially in the hotel sector which has high risks related to interaction with guests and use of equipment. This research aims to examine the influence of K3 on employee performance at The Westin Hotel Jakarta. The method used is quantitative research with a simple regression approach. The research sample consisted of 40 employees selected by accidental sampling, with data collected using a questionnaire which was measured using a Likert scale. The results of partial hypothesis testing show that occupational health and safety have a significant effect on employee performance. This shows that good implementation of occupational health and safety can increase employee motivation, efficiency and work quality. Based on the research results, it is recommended that employees continue to participate in occupational health and safety training and actively provide input regarding its implementation. Hotel management is also advised to strengthen occupational health and safety policies through regular training, provision of personal protective equipment, and regular evaluations to ensure consistent implementation. With these steps, it is hoped that employee performance can improve so as to create a more productive and safe work environment.

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KEYWORDS: Health and safety, Hotel management, Employee performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The hotel industry, especially five-star hotels, is one of the sectors that is growing rapidly in Indonesia (Syaputri et al., 2021). In the midst of increasingly fierce competition, luxury hotels such as The Westin Jakarta are required to provide the best service to guests, which not only involves the quality of facilities, but also the quality of service provided by employees (Saipuloh & Surono, 2023). One of the factors that influences employee performance is Occupational Health and Safety implemented by the company. Occupational health and safety in the hospitality sector functions not only to prevent work injuries or accidents, but also to improve the physical and mental well-being of employees, which ultimately contributes to their performance (Prastowo, 2017). The Westin Jakarta Hotel, as one of the luxury hotels in Indonesia, is a relevant example for analyzing how occupational health and safety can affect employee productivity and work quality.

The main problem faced in the hotel industry is the high level of stress, fatigue and risk of work injury faced by employees. Staff working in various departments, such as housekeeping, kitchen, and guest services, often have to deal

with work environments with high physical and mental demands. This condition could risk reducing their performance, and even affect the quality of service provided to guests (Azizah & Faras, 2024). Therefore, it is important to explore the extent to which occupational health and safety can play a role in improving employee welfare, reducing absenteeism due to health problems, and reducing turnover rates (Bhastary & Suwardi, 2018).

The purpose of this research is to analyze the influence of occupational health and safety on employee performance at The Westin Hotel Jakarta. This research will focus on how occupational health and safety implemented by hotel management contributes to improving the physical and mental well-being of employees, as well as its impact on the quality of service provided to guests. Specifically, this research will examine specific factors in occupational health and safety, such as safety training, provision of health facilities, and management of work stress, and how these factors can be directly related to employee productivity, motivation, and job satisfaction. With this aim, this research is expected to provide useful insights for human resource management in five-star hotels and enrich the literature on

occupational health and safety in the hotel sector. This research seeks to answer these questions in a more holistic way, integrating the physical, mental and social aspects of occupational health and safety, as well as their impact on more specific employee performance, namely The Westin Hotel Jakarta.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Occupational Health and Safety Concept

Occupational health and safety is a system designed to protect workers from accidents and illnesses that can occur during work. Occupational health and safety includes various efforts to prevent, overcome and monitor all types of risks that could endanger the safety and health of workers. In the hotel industry, occupational health and safety is very important because employees interact with various risk factors, such as the use of sharp kitchen equipment, exposure to cleaning chemicals, and direct interaction with guests who have high expectations of service quality (Atiyah & Wibowo, 2023).

In Indonesia, the implementation of occupational health and safety in the workplace is regulated by Law no. 1 of 1970 concerning work safety which states that every company is obliged to create a safe and healthy work environment for its employees. In the hotel sector, although the risks faced are not as large as other industrial sectors, work involving direct interaction with guests, facility management and hotel operations still requires special attention to appropriate occupational health and safety standards.

Occupational Health and Safety in the Hospitality Sector

The hotel sector has its own challenges in implementation. Hotels often face difficulties in balancing efficient operational management with adequate implementation. Hotel workers are often faced with demanding physical conditions, such as working for long hours, standing or walking all day, and interacting with various potentially dangerous equipment and materials. On the other hand, psychological factors such as work stress and pressure to provide perfect service are also part of the risks that must be managed well (Istriarto, 2021). Implementing good occupational health and safety can have a positive impact on job satisfaction and employee motivation. Companies that prioritize work safety and employee welfare tend to have lower turnover rates and more employees are satisfied with their jobs. Proper risk management in the workplace, including in terms of occupational health and safety, can increase employee productivity and reduce absenteeism due to injuries or other health problems (Dewi & Fardinal, 2021).

The Relationship between Occupational Health and Safety and Employee Performance

Several studies indicate that good occupational health and safety not only serves to prevent work accidents and

injuries, but also has a broader positive impact on employee performance. Maintained physical and mental well-being will increase work morale, motivation and loyalty to the company, which ultimately results in an increase in the quality of service provided to guests (Sari et al., 2023). Research by Parashakti & Putriawati (2020) found that safety that involves active employee participation in decision making can increase their commitment to safety and overall productivity.

One important aspect of occupational health and safety is managing work stress, which can have a major impact on employee well-being. Research by Malau & Ratnawati (2024) revealed that high work stress can reduce concentration, work quality, and increase absenteeism, which of course affects overall performance. On the other hand, occupational health and safety that prioritizes support for employee mental health, such as stress management programs, can increase work motivation and productivity. In relation to the hotel sector, employees must be faced with high expectations from guests and busy work demands.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a type of quantitative research, which aims to test and analyze the relationship between independent and dependent variables. In this case, this research will measure the influence of Occupational Health and Safety on employee performance at The Westin Jakarta Hotel. Quantitative research focuses more on collecting numerical data and statistical analysis to identify relationships or influences between the variables studied. The method used in this research is simple regression. Simple regression was chosen because this research aims to determine the extent to which occupational health and safety implemented at The Westin Jakarta Hotel affects employee performance. By using simple regression, the relationship between one independent variable (work health and safety) and one dependent variable (employee performance) can be explained. This simple regression model will provide information about the magnitude of the influence of occupational health and safety on employee performance, as well as how much occupational health and safety contributes to the observed changes in performance.

The population in this study are all employees who work at The Westin Jakarta Hotel, consisting of various departments, such as housekeeping, food and beverage, front office, and others. Because the number of employees working at this hotel is quite large, this research will take a representative sample from this population. According to Sugiyono (2017), the appropriate number of respondents for quantitative research using sampling techniques that do not require complicated sample calculations, ideally ranges from 30 to 500 respondents. In this case, this research will use a sample of 40 employees from various departments at The Westin Hotel Jakarta. Sampling was carried out using the

Accidental Sampling technique, where respondents were selected by chance or based on their availability at the time the research was conducted. This makes it possible to obtain data from employees who are directly involved in hotel operations and have experience related to applied occupational health and safety.

The data collection technique in this research uses a questionnaire distributed to employees who have been selected as samples. This questionnaire was designed to measure the two main variables in this research, namely: (1) Measured by questions related to the implementation of occupational health and safety in hotels, such as safety training, provision of personal protective equipment, and attention to employee health; (2) Measured by questions related to employee perceptions of their own performance, such as productivity, service quality, and job satisfaction. The questionnaire uses a Likert scale with 5 answer choices, namely: (1) Strongly Disagree; (2) Disagree; (3) Disagree; (4) Agree; (5) Strongly Agree.

This Likert scale makes it possible to measure the respondent's level of agreement or disagreement with the statements given, so as to produce data that can be analyzed quantitatively. Data collected from the questionnaire will be analyzed using various statistical techniques which include the following stages: (1) Validity tests are carried out to measure the extent to which the questionnaire used in this research is able to measure the variables in question; (2) Reliability testing aims to measure the consistency and stability of measuring instruments; (3) The coefficient of determination test is used to see how much influence the independent variable (work health and safety) has on the dependent variable (employee performance); (4) This hypothesis test is used to test the hypothesis proposed in this research. The hypothesis tested is whether occupational health and safety have a significant effect on employee performance at The Westin Hotel Jakarta.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Respondents

Karakteristik	Kategori	Jumlah (n=40)	Responden Persentase (%)
Gender	Male	18	45%
	Female	22	55%
Age	18–25 years old	10	25%
	26–35 years old	15	37,5%
	36–45 years old	8	20%
	> 46 years old	7	17,5%
Division	Front Office	10	25%
	Food & Beverage	15	37,5%
	Housekeeping	15	37,5%
Length of work	1–3 years	12	30%
	4–6 years	15	37,5%
	> 7 years	13	32,5%
Education	High School	7	17,5%
	Diploma	10	25%
	Bachelor	23	57,5%
Work health and safety training experience	Have attended occupational health and safety training	40	100%
Level of Understanding of occupational health and safety	High	20	50%
	Sufficient	15	37,5%
	Low	5	12,5%

Source: Processed data (2024)

Most of the respondents were women, namely 55%, while the other 45% were men. This division reflects the gender composition that is often found in the hotel industry,

where service and front office positions are mostly filled by women. Most respondents were in the 26–35 year age range (37.5%), which reflects the productive age group in the

world of work. In addition, 25% of respondents were in the 18–25 year age range, which shows that there is a young workforce who are just entering the world of work. Only 17.5% of respondents were aged 46 years and over, which shows that most employees are relatively young, but there are also those who are more experienced. Respondents were spread across three main hotel divisions: Front Office (25%), Food & Beverage (37.5%), and Housekeeping (37.5%). This division shows the diversity of experience and tasks held by respondents in hotels, as well as the various challenges faced by employees in each division related to implementing occupational health and safety.

Most respondents (37.5%) have worked in hotels for 4–6 years, indicating that they have quite a long time of experience in the hotel industry. Around 32.5% of respondents have worked in hotels for more than 7 years, indicating that there are experienced employees who can provide more insight into the occupational health and safety practices implemented. Meanwhile, 30% of respondents have only worked between 1-3 years, which can also provide a fresh perspective regarding occupational health and safety implemented during their work period. Most respondents had a bachelor's degree (57.5%), followed by a

diploma (25%), and high school/vocational school (17.5%). This shows that most of The Westin Jakarta Hotel employees have a fairly high educational background, which might make it easier for them to understand and implement occupational health and safety more effectively.

All respondents have attended occupational health and safety training, which shows the hotel's commitment to ensuring that all employees understand the importance of occupational safety and health in the workplace. This also shows that occupational health and safety training is an integral part of the safety implemented by hotel management. The majority of respondents have a good level of understanding about occupational health and safety implemented in this hotel. As many as 50% of respondents had a high level of understanding, while another 37.5% had a fairly good understanding. Only 12.5% of respondents felt they had a low understanding of occupational health and safety. This shows that although the majority of employees already understand occupational health and safety well enough, there are still a small number who may need additional explanation or training to improve their understanding.

Table 2. Validity Test Results

No.	Quisioner Item	r-count	r-table
Kesehatan dan Keselamatan Kerja			
1	I feel that I have received sufficient occupational health and safety training at work.	0.651	0.312
2	I feel that the occupational health and safety training received is sufficient to reduce work risks.	0.580	0.312
3	The company provides adequate personal protective equipment in the workplace.	0.727	0.312
4	Occupational health and safety at this hotel is clear and easy to understand for me.	0.671	0.312
5	I feel safer at work after following occupational health and safety.	0.700	0.312
6	I often get the latest information regarding occupational health and safety.	0.626	0.312
7	Occupational health and safety in companies helps prevent workplace accidents.	0.755	0.312
8	The company carries out routine inspections to ensure the implementation of occupational health and safety.	0.683	0.312
9	I was given the opportunity to provide input regarding occupational health and safety.	0.642	0.312
10	Occupational health and safety are consistently implemented in the workplace.	0.691	0.312
Employee performance			
11	I feel I can complete the work efficiently.	0.612	0.312
12	I feel I can achieve the targets set by the company.	0.550	0.312
13	I am satisfied with the quality of service I provide to guests.	0.639	0.312
14	I feel that my performance is appreciated by my superiors.	0.597	0.312

No. Quisioner Item		r-count	r-table
15	I feel motivated to work better after attending occupational health and safety training.	0.528	0.312
16	I feel more confident in doing my job after occupational health and safety training.	0.564	0.312
17	Occupational health and safety training contributes to improving the quality of my work.	0.665	0.312
18	I feel I can work faster after taking occupational health and safety training.	0.602	0.312
19	Occupational health and safety training improves my occupational safety at work.	0.647	0.312
20	Occupational health and safety training helps me adapt to changes in work.	0.656	0.312

Source: Processed data (2024)

All question items on the two variables in table 2, namely occupational health and safety and employee

performance, are declared valid because the calculated r-value for each item is greater than the r-table (0.312).

Table 3. Reliability Test Results (Cronbach's Alpha)

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Alpha Value
Occupational Health and Safety	0,876	0.600
Employee performance	0,818	0.600

Source: Processed data (2024)

Based on the reliability test results presented in Table 3, it can be concluded that the two variables in this study, namely occupational health and safety and employee performance, have a good level of reliability. The Cronbach's alpha value for occupational health and safety is

0.876 and for employee performance is 0.818, both of which are much greater than the accepted reliability threshold value, namely 0.600. This shows that the questionnaire instruments for these two variables are reliable and consistent in measuring the construct in question.

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination

R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
0.790	0.624	0.602	0.35488999

Source: Processed data (2024)

The Adjusted R Square value of 0.602 can be seen in Table 4 which shows that after considering the number of

variables in the model, around 60.2% of employee performance is influenced by occupational health and safety.

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.234	0.328		3.761	0.001
Occupational Health and Safety	0.512	0.098	0.632	5.229	0.000

Source: Processed data (2024)

Based on the results of the hypothesis test presented in Table 5, there is significant evidence regarding the influence of occupational health and safety on the dependent variable. The t value for occupational health and safety is 5.229 with Sig. of 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level of

0.05, indicating that occupational health and safety has a significant influence.

Occupational health and safety have a significant influence on employee performance at The Westin Jakarta Hotel because good occupational health and safety can

create a safe work environment and support employee well-being, which in turn can increase their motivation, focus and productivity. With adequate occupational health and safety training, clarity regarding safety, employees feel more confident in carrying out their duties, reduce anxiety regarding potential risks, and increase job satisfaction. This is reflected in the results of the hypothesis test which shows that occupational health and safety has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, as evidenced by the t value of 5.229 and Sig. 0.000 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, as well as a coefficient that shows a significant contribution in improving their performance.

Several previous studies have shown that occupational health and safety have a significant influence on employee performance. Research by Rahmadhani et al. (2021) and Nugraha & Nurhayati (2016) in the hotel industry found that occupational health and safety implemented consistently can increase employee productivity and efficiency, by reducing work accidents and increasing motivation. Putra et al. (2019) also showed similar results in a Surabaya construction company, where good occupational health and safety was closely related to increased work quality and task completion time. In addition, Nugraha & Yulia (2019) revealed that routine occupational health and safety training improves employee performance at Indonesian Railways, while Wulandari et al. (2023) found that effective occupational health and safety can reduce the incidence of work accidents, thereby increasing employee productivity and overall performance. All of this research is in line with research at The Westin Jakarta Hotel, which shows that occupational health and safety has a positive effect on employee performance, both in terms of safety, motivation and work efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this research, it can be concluded that occupational health and safety have a significant effect on employee performance at The Westin Hotel Jakarta. The results of the validity test show that all question items in the questionnaire are valid, while the reliability test shows that the instrument used has good consistency. The results of the hypothesis test show that the occupational health and safety implemented at this hotel has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, both in terms of motivation, efficiency and quality of work. In addition, analysis of the coefficient of determination shows that occupational health and safety can explain most of the variation in employee performance. Thus, effective occupational health and safety can contribute to improving employee performance in hospitality environments.

Employees are advised to continue participating in training and programs related to occupational health and safety provided by hotel management. Increasing

understanding and skills related to work safety can help increase self-confidence, reduce the risk of accidents, and improve overall performance. Employees are also advised to actively provide input regarding occupational health and safety, so that it is more relevant and effective.

The management of The Westin Jakarta Hotel is advised to continue to strengthen occupational health and safety by providing regular training, adequate personal protective equipment, and ensuring that occupational health and safety is implemented consistently in all operational lines. In addition, management should carry out regular evaluations of work health and safety and optimize communication with employees so that they feel safer and are motivated to improve their performance. Improving the quality and effectiveness of occupational health and safety can contribute to creating a more productive and safe work environment for all employees.

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